

Classroom Case Study: Cross Cultural Obstacles to the Referral of Aboriginal Children for Hearing Tests

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Hearing loss is endemic among Aboriginal children because of persistent middle ear disease. If compensating communication strategies and support programs are to be engaged, a child's hearing loss needs to be identified. Teacher recommendations are an important source of referrals for hearing tests, with school screening programs now being infrequent or nonexistent. However, cultural differences in Aboriginal children's attentional styles, together with some children with hearing loss using more face-watching as a compensatory strategy, can confuse non-Aboriginal teachers as to who may need referral for hearing testing. This article describes a classroom case study that found culturally different attentional styles and compensatory face-watching, similar to that described in a remote school, among some urban Aboriginal children. The attentiveness of one child with hearing loss confused teachers. The implication for the identification of Aboriginal children's hearing loss is discussed.

There is increasing evidence of the adverse social and educational effects of Conductive Hearing Loss (CHL), especially among Aboriginal children who experience endemic levels of the condition. CHL amongst Aboriginal children has been found to be associated with diminished social and emotional wellbeing (Zubrick et al., 2004), antisocial behaviour at school (Howard, 1990; 2004), lower levels of achievement at school (Yonovitz & Yonovitz, 2000; Howard, 2004) and greater levels of absenteeism (Couzos et al., 2003). It is estimated that, on

average, Aboriginal children spend two and a half years during childhood with CHL, compared to three months for non-Aboriginal children in Australia (OATSIH, 2001).

Identification of children's hearing loss is necessary if compensatory strategies and support programs can be engaged. Referral for audiological assessment is necessary to identify current CHL. Identification of CHL generally results from primary screening programs. Individual referrals, on the other hand, take place when parents, teachers or others suspect a hearing loss.

McPherson (1995) reported that the states with large Aboriginal populations (Queensland, Northern Territory and Western Australia) mainly had screening programs for non-urban areas. There were fewer screening programs for Aboriginal children in urban areas, despite the fact that 67% of Aboriginal children live in urban areas (Australia Bureau Statistics, 1993).

McPherson (1995) suggested that the absence of screening in urban areas is related to (a) the fact that mass screening is easier and more cost effective when a population group is in close geographical proximity. In urban areas, Aboriginal children are scattered throughout the mainstream population, as opposed to their peers in rural settlements; (b) The relative 'visibility' of hearing loss where health services only service Aboriginal clients.

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However, hearing screening programs are resource intensive and, even in remote areas, are becoming less frequent, if they take place at all. In some areas, hearing screening is not carried out as it is thought to be unethical where later referral for full audiological assessment and appropriate intervention is not an option

In urban areas, identification of hearing loss has been mostly reliant on the referral of individual Aboriginal children for hearing tests. Often, non-Aboriginal professionals, mostly teachers, make these referrals on the basis of a child's attentiveness. *However, this may not be a reliable indicator of hearing loss for Aboriginal children.*

Cultural Differences in Attentiveness

Many Aboriginal people make less eye contact than westerners (Eades, 1992; Harris, 1976) and misunderstandings often arise because of crosscultural misinterpretation of what this signifies. Many non-Aboriginal people are offended when first addressing Aboriginal community meetings, where people often wander around and making little eye contact with the speaker. This response is commonly interpreted by non-Aboriginal people as indicating disrespect or disinterest. In the criminal justice system, judiciary and jurors are warned about making judgments as to guilt or honesty on the basis of demeanor such as eye contact (Eades, 1992). Conversely, many Aboriginal people find the intense gaze of a polite non-Aboriginal audience highly disconcerting.

This was illustrated in the opening of an art exhibition in Darwin observed by the author. The Tiwi island artists were placed facing the audience during the opening. There was noticeable discomfort among the artists at the polite, unrelenting gaze of the audience. Gradually, and as a group, the Tiwi artists turned around so, by the end of the official opening, they had their backs turned to the audience. Speaking with some of the artists later they confirmed that the intense watching by the audience had upset them.

Maintaining less eye contact during social interaction with their teachers is also evident among many — but not all — Aboriginal schoolchildren. Lowell (1994) described different attentional styles among Aboriginal students in a remote bilingual school. She found many Aboriginal children paid attention to their teachers, despite behaving in ways that non-Aboriginal teachers associate with lack of attention (i.e., students made little eye contact and moved around the class, but were nonetheless paying attention). Some children, meanwhile, made more eye contact with their teachers — some children with CHL. These children were using face-watching and lip-reading to compensate for limited auditory input. Lowell (1994) described that face-watching was most evident among the children who experienced most persistent conductive hearing loss.

The variety of eye contact patterns demonstrated by Aboriginal children may be quite confusing for non-Aboriginal teachers. Given their experience with non-Aboriginal children, teachers would expect greater eye contact to signify good attention and no hearing loss; while inattentiveness, as measured by less eye contact, would signify possible hearing problems. However, hearing tests may reveal that the reverse of these teacher assumptions is true. Some Aboriginal children who face-watch to compensate for hearing loss appear 'attentive', while other Aboriginal children with no hearing loss, but with a different attentional style, appear 'inattentive' to non-Aboriginal teachers. Lowell (1994) observed these type of responses among Aboriginal children who lived in a remote community and attended a school where they were mostly taught by Aboriginal teachers who were aware of cultural differences in attentional styles. In this context, crosscultural misunderstanding is unlikely. However, Aboriginal children in Australia are mostly taught by non-Aboriginal teachers. It may be that crosscultural misunderstanding is either more probable in this crosscultural context or less likely because of the greater familiarity of

urban Aboriginal children with western sociocultural etiquette. The following classroom case study sought to identify, first, if cultural differences in attentiveness (as measured by the amount of eye contact) was evident between Aboriginal and non-Aboriginal children in an urban school during one-to-one conversation with their non-Aboriginal teacher. Second, it sought to examine if the attentiveness style of urban Aboriginal children with a current CHL differed to that of urban Aboriginal children with no hearing loss.

METHOD

To consider this issue further a case study of the structured one-to-one social interaction between a teacher and a number of her students, whose current hearing status was known, was arranged. The focus of the case study was the amount of time children made eye contact while talking one-to-one with their teacher, who was asked to discuss recent school project work with students. The teacher and students (9) were video recorded conversing, sitting on chairs set up one metre apart outside the classroom, in a relatively (for schools) quiet environment (between 60 dB SPL–70 dB SPL). The amount of time

each student spent watching the face of the teacher during the conversations was then timed with a stopwatch. Since CHL fluctuates — making knowledge of children's current hearing status crucial — there was limited time to organise this project soon after hearing screenings took place at the school. This meant only a small group of similar aged children from one classroom was able to be involved. The nine students involved were three Aboriginal students with current bilateral hearing loss, three Aboriginal students and three non-Aboriginal students without current hearing loss. These children were chosen as Aboriginal and non-Aboriginal students who had passed their hearing screenings and were closest in age to the Aboriginal students with a bilateral hearing loss. Children's hearing status was identified on the basis of all children in the class having their hearing assessed by pure tone audiometry (at 0.5, 1, 2 and 4 kHz) carried out in a soundproof booth, as well as simple otoscopy and tympanometry. Children who failed the screening (> 25 dB HL) were given a full hearing assessment.

The percentage of time each student spent watching the face of the teacher during the conversations is presented in Figure 1.

FIGURE 1
Percentage of time each subject spent watching face of the teacher.

The three Aboriginal students with no current hearing loss spent approximately half as much time face-watching as the three non-Aboriginal students with no hearing loss. This different pattern of visual attention among these urban Aboriginal students with no hearing loss is similar to that described by Lowell (1994) amongst traditionally oriented Aboriginal students in a remote community.

However, two of the three urban Aboriginal students with current hearing loss maintained eye contact more than the three Aboriginal students with no current hearing loss, probably as compensatory visual communication strategy — face-watching. This meant they resembled the non-Aboriginal children with no hearing loss in their visual attentiveness during one-to-one conversation with their teacher. Since Lowell (1994) described this type of face-watching as most evident among children with more persistent conductive hearing loss, it is likely that the other Aboriginal student with current hearing loss, who maintained eye contact only 30% of the time, may not have experienced persistent conductive hearing loss.

Overall, the results of this case study suggest that the type of culturally shaped differences identified by Lowell (1994) among some Aboriginal students in remote communities is also evident among some urban Aboriginal students. Further, the responses of some children with current hearing loss in making eye contact is likely to be confusing for teachers who use visual attention as an indicator of good hearing. This was supported by interviews with teachers.

The teachers of one of the Aboriginal students (Kirsty) who worked in the same classroom team teaching were surprised to discover she had a hearing loss, seeing her as one of 'the attentive good listeners'.

T 1: Well, you watch her there on the floor and she really does pay attention, but Kirsty doesn't produce does she?

T 2: No, she always listens very hard, but her work doesn't show that. You look over at the table and she's always busy doing something. She's not wandering and

wondering what to do next. She knows what to do.

T 1: I hadn't thought of her as having problems [with hearing] because she always paid attention. She said to me 'my mum said I must be a bit deaf' and I said, 'why's that?' and she said 'because I don't always hear what she says'. So I said, 'Oh do you hear what I say during class?' and she sort of looked a bit sheepish and said 'no, not always'. And I was really, really surprised. She was one of my best listeners.

T 2: She usually sits in the same place, near the front, she never puts herself at the back or at the side. She doesn't mess around, she watches. She doesn't fiddle with her dress or shoelaces or anything like that. She gives the impression that she's brighter than she is really.

T 1: Kirsty is always sitting in the right place looking at the right person. She wants to do it nicely. She tries so hard. I had no idea that she was having any difficulty.

Kirsty's apparent attention had led her teachers to assume she had no hearing problems and they were quite surprised to find that she did. Kirsty's attempts to visually compensate for hearing loss matched her teachers' culturally-based expectations of good attention, signifying good hearing. Her teachers had resolved the inconsistency between her apparent attentiveness and poor performance by concluding, 'she gives the impression she's brighter than she really is'.

DISCUSSION

These results suggest that the cultural differences in attentional style found by Lowell (1994) in a remote school are also evident among some urban Aboriginal students. The culturally shaped visual attentiveness style among Aboriginal students with no hearing loss, together with the compensatory face-watching among some Aboriginal students with current hearing loss means there may be systematic errors when non-Aboriginal adults use visual attentiveness to determine which

Aboriginal children may need to be referred to have their hearing tested. Many Aboriginal children with current hearing loss may not be referred for hearing tests, while Aboriginal children with good hearing may be referred because their apparent poor attentiveness is mistakenly thought to be related to hearing loss.

Crosscultural misunderstanding of attentional behaviour may help to explain some apparently paradoxical research results where data was based on non-Aboriginal teachers' perceptions of Aboriginal students' attention. Lewis (1976), in an often reported study, described that Aboriginal children with hearing loss demonstrated greater 'linguistic incompetence'. He also found a paradoxical negative correlation between Aboriginal children's teacher-identified attention and their reading ability: The students identified by teachers to demonstrate the best 'attention' in class were poorer readers than those who seemed to pay little attention in class.

The otherwise inexplicable association between attentiveness in class and limited reading skills makes sense if considered on the basis of crosscultural misinterpretation of visual attentional styles. This would suggest what was being measured is an association between Aboriginal students' limited reading ability and the use of face-watching as a visual compensation strategies by students with persistent hearing loss. This is a more plausible explanation of the results and is consistent with findings of an association between CHL and limited literacy among Aboriginal children (Walker & Wigglesworth, 2001; Yonovitz & Yonovitz, 2000).

It is also worth noting how the teachers interviewed explained Kristy's poor school performance, despite her attentiveness at school. The discrepancy between her classroom attentiveness, and poor performance was resolved by a judgment about her ability — 'she's not as bright as she appears'. It is well established that teachers' beliefs about student's ability influence students' actual performance — the Pygmalion effect (Rosenthal & Jacobson, 1968). Work in Aboriginal education indicates that

Aboriginal students' educational opportunities are especially influenced by non-Aboriginal teacher's attitudes towards them (Malin, 1990). Such teacher judgments about children with hearing loss may compound the direct educational disadvantage of hearing related communication problems. This highlights the importance of teacher awareness of which children have hearing loss so they can both implement compensatory communication strategies, as well as avoid inaccurate judgments about their educational capacity.

This study supports the importance of regular school hearing screening for Aboriginal children. Without formal screening, crosscultural misunderstanding is likely to inhibit appropriate teacher referrals of Aboriginal children for hearing tests. It also indicates the need to make teachers aware of possible behavioural indicators of Aboriginal children's hearing loss. McPherson (1995) found the best behavioural indicator of hearing loss among urban Aboriginal students was having social problems with peers. Excessive teasing was also found to be associated with a current hearing loss among students in remote schools (Howard, 2004). Teacher-directed speech reception games (Howard, 1993) have also been found to help overcome the crosscultural masking of Aboriginal children's hearing loss. There are also implications for the pre- and postservice training of teachers to include, firstly, information on cultural differences in attentional styles and secondly, that care should be taken not to judge students' abilities on the basis of discrepancies between attentiveness and poor performance.

AUTHOR NOTE

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